

Original Research

How Attractive is the Participation in an Energy Community? Evidence and Recommendations from a Conjoint Study

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Declarations

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

Studies reported in this article were approved by the local Ethics Committee at the University of Graz (identifier: GZ. 39/44/63 ex 2020/21) in accordance with the §2 (4) Statute of the Ethics Commission. Informed consent to participate (in line with the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union) was obtained from all participants.

Data Availability and Open Science

All materials, anonymized data, and codes are available from the Open Science Framework: https://osf.io/853pe/overview?view_only=ca293d16e9ee4488b9aa2904825632ed

All studies were preregistered before data analysis:

Main study: https://osf.io/s3f42/overview?view_only=5f693813bc97459998735eff36e48a69;

Pilot study: https://osf.io/9yd5m/overview?view_only=277f376d88f9427c92696973f98b8115

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Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is declared by the authors.

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Author contribution

HB prepared and revised the materials, conducted the pre study and main study, conducted the analysis for both studies, and wrote the manuscript; JH, JB and KC gave feedback on the study design and suggested corrections in the manuscript; EM provided input for the theoretical background; CRA provided technical support to set up the conjoint study

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Abstract

Energy communities are gaining prominence across Europe, but little is known about factors that motivate individuals to join them. This study investigates how social, legal, technical factors, as well as person-specific characteristics shape motivation to participate in ECs beyond financial considerations. Using a conjoint experimental design in an Austrian online survey ($N = 554$), we examined preferences across multiple EC profiles per person. Results indicate that participants slightly preferred ECs organized as associations over corporate or company-based entities, and favored comprehensive energy usage models (e.g., combining electricity and heating) over more narrowly focused applications. There was also limited evidence for a preference toward socially diverse communities. At the individual level, motivation to join an EC was most strongly associated with positive attitudes toward public service, followed by weaker effects of future orientation and biospheric values. We discuss the results in the light of emerging perspectives on energy citizenship, highlighting individuals as active contributors rather than passive consumers in the energy transition.

Keywords: energy community, participation, energy citizenship, incentives, green energy

Background

Energy Communities (ECs) increasingly become a topic of scientific and political debate in many parts of Europe as a decentralized form of energy management (Aruta et al., 2023; Ahmed et al., 2024). They are expected to play a pivotal role in the energy transition, contributing to a low-carbon, secure, affordable, and renewable energy system (Koirala et al., 2018; Lennon et al., 2020). In such ECs, different stakeholders like citizens, citizen associations, companies, or municipalities convene to locally organize their energy generation and consumption. However, the concept of EC is multifaceted and subject to varying interpretations across Europe (Walker & Devine-Wright, 2008; Walker, 2011). While some ECs fall under the formal categories of “Citizen Energy Communities” and “Renewable Energy Communities”, as introduced by the European Commission in Directive (EU) 2019/944, others include more informal and grassroots initiatives that may not meet these specific criteria (Bauwens et al., 2022). As a result, ECs can take on very different forms across different countries and contexts. This includes variations in governance structures, technological integration (Boon et al., 2014), legal and economic frameworks (Bertel, 2022), geographical scale, and the kinds of actors involved (Hannoset et al., 2019). Despite this heterogeneity, participation rates in such ECs have only increased marginally in Europe (Schwanitz et al., 2023). This raises an important question: How do people perceive these different compositions and profiles of ECs, and which characteristics make them more or less appealing for potential members? In this research, we investigated the preferences of people regarding several aspects of ECs, which might be attractive to them.

In Europe, market prizes for green energy devices, particularly photovoltaic, have decreased dramatically over the course of the last decades, which sparked an interest in the public to make use of green energy. Austria is a prominent example for a country, where ECs seem to have become more viable for people: Directives from the EU level were implemented early into national law, enabling the establishment of ECs by private individuals, small and medium-sized enterprises, or local authorities without primarily aiming for profit. As participants benefited more from reduced grid fees, financial subsidies, and other support measures, approximately 1170 renewable ECs were established between 2021 and 24 and the number continues to rise.

Beyond sole market pricing, ECs may offer a broad scope of social, legal and technical features to consider, which may or may not affect people’s motivation to join an EC. They, hence, create barriers for engagement for people beyond their specific preferences and attitudes, which will be addressed further below. We identified three dimensions of EC features that we consider relevant for people’s decision to partake in an EC and which we want to focus on in this study (see Goedkoop et al. 2023; Malakhatka et al., 2026) and which were also highlighted in other research (e.g., De Lotto et al., 2022; Lazaroiu et al., 2025).

Social dimension

The social configurations of ECs can vary significantly, and this variation could play a crucial role in shaping individuals' willingness to join. Research has shown that community engagement and social dynamics are central to the success of such initiatives. For example, Lopes and Antunes (2022) highlight how social acceptance and participation are closely linked to the degree of community involvement and the perceived inclusiveness of the project. A key differentiator among ECs is who initiates, owns, and participates in them. Some ECs are entirely resident-led, while others involve collaborations between citizens, local governments, and small or medium-sized enterprises. Studies suggest that ECs initiated by local residents, either alone or alongside public actors, tend to foster stronger motivation among potential members compared to communities established solely by external actors such as governments or corporations (Jans, 2021). This may be because locally led initiatives offer more opportunities for interaction, political representation, and a sense of belonging (Lickel et al., 2000, Held & Corcoran, 2025). Another aspect that may vary between different ECs is the time people need to invest into the EC. While time commitment can foster social identification and a deeper sense of involvement, which makes the group feel more meaningful and less permeable (Lickel et al., 2000), it can also present as a barrier, deterring participation from outsiders if they perceive it as too demanding. Furthermore, the diversity of an EC and its members might be a factor influencing people's perceptions of ECs. Although educational and income diversity can enrich group perspectives and broaden reach (Mennis et al., 2013), it may also lead to lower perceived group cohesion and identity, which in turn can reduce motivation to participate (van Zomeren et al., 2008; Lickel et al., 2000).

Legal dimension

Psychological research indicates that groups may be perceived as more motivated to engage in certain behaviors, if they are based on a legally binding contract among members, because contracts may signal social norms (i.e., what is the appropriate and actually practiced behavior, see Eisner et al., 2021). In Austria, there are three legal forms that an EC can take, each offering different structural and participatory features. An association (in German: *Verein*) is a common and accessible form, often used for non-profit and community-driven initiatives where decision-making is typically democratic. A cooperative (*Genossenschaft*) places strong emphasis on joint ownership and economic participation, with members having both a financial stake and voting rights. Lastly, a limited liability company (*Gemeinschaft mit beschränkter Haftung, GmbH*) provides a more formalized and business-oriented framework, usually involving fewer members and a clearer hierarchical structure. These legal forms to organized behavior shape not only how ECs are governed, but may also influence how attractive and inclusive they appear to potential participants. For instance, one could argue that a company structure could be most attractive to people as clear hierarchies in obligations may be preferred. At the same time, association may have more benefits for more effective, trust-based exchanges among members (see Artis et al., 2025).

Technical dimension

In addition to social and legal differences, ECs can vary significantly in their technological configurations, which concern aspects of the local grid and energy management, as well as specifics about the production and consumption of the energy (see, e.g., De Lotto et al., 2022; Lazaroiu et al., 2025; Malakhatka et al., 2026). A common feature is the integration of renewable energy sources, often combined with small-scale energy storage systems to improve local energy autonomy and resilience. For example, some EC models aim to optimize microgrid efficiency by balancing environmental concerns, energy management needs, and economic considerations (Ceglia et al., 2022a, 2022b). Some ECs optimize their energy use by utilizing energy for multiple functions such as heating, cooling, and electricity while other ECs focus on a single, centralized purpose like electricity. Furthermore, ECs can also differ in how much control members have over technical operations. In some communities, systems are technically optimized, fully automated and managed exclusively by experts, while members themselves cannot interfere. On the other hand, some ECs grant members full control over technical functions, requiring active coordination and decision-making but ensuring greater privacy by avoiding automated systems. There are several of these technological design choices that not only shape how ECs operate but likely also influence who feels capable, secure, and motivated to participate.

Person-specific factors

There is also evidence that the public experienced a rising awareness of environmental issues and developed stronger pro-environmental attitudes over time (European Commission, 2024; Bauske et al., 2022). And as young generations started protesting for the environment in 2019, just as the EU called for a Green Deal (Fetting, 2020), parts of the older generations seemed to adjust their behavior towards green values as well (Fabel et al., 2025). Therefore, the growing popularity of sustainable energy usage is potentially not only driven by technological progress or falling prices, but also reflects broader societal changes: more and more people are looking for ways to take ownership of their energy future – making choices that reflect their values, connecting with others in their communities, and finding local solutions that feel both practical and meaningful.

ECs may offer a practical way to do just that: They create space for citizens to engage directly in energy production and decision-making. As awareness of climate change has grown, so too has the appeal of models that combine ecological goals with local democratic empowerment, as reflected in European laws (Directive 2024/825, European Union, 2024), which envision citizens moving beyond passive consumer roles and offer them a more agentic role in the energy system. The idea that people perceive rights and responsibilities to participate in shaping a just and sustainable energy transition and feel motivated to act accordingly is also known as *energy citizenship* (Devine-Wright, 2007; Ryghaug et al., 2018; Hamann et al., 2023). In many ways, ECs are not just energy projects, but part of a wider cultural shift toward more sustainable, resilient, and community-oriented ways of living (International Energy Agency, 2023). And indeed, previous research (Sloot et al., 2019)

indicates that the strongest motivations for people to become involved in ECs are rooted in both environmental motives (wanting to protect the environment) as well as communal motives for more social justice (wanting to be involved in a community).

For this exploratory study, we wanted to account for such person-specific effects by integrating a set of scales that, in our view, could further illuminate participants' motivation:

Biospheric values. Introduced by De Groot and Steg (2007, 2008), biospheric values should accompany basic values, seen as guiding principles of individuals. These principles imply a strong caring for nature and were used as predictor of several pro-environmental intentions and behaviors in the past (Bouman et al., 2018; Van der Werff & Steg, 2016; Brohmer et al., 2023a). As joining an EC functions as a mean to more pro-environmental behavior, biospheric values may turn out as a relevant predictor.

Public service attitudes. This concept depicts the individual inclination to be drawn to services benefiting the community (Kim et al., 2013; Witesman et al., 2022).¹ This way, it also relates to contemporary environmental research that highlights the importance of communal belonging and identity as driver to engage in environmental action (e.g., Fritsche et al., 2018; Hamann et al., 2023). ECs provide a ground, where individuals can act in a community for the environment in a sustainable and long-lasting way.

Consideration of future and immediate consequences. People high in future orientation tend to value long-term outcomes and are therefore more likely to engage in future-oriented pro-environmental behavior, even when it involves short-term inconvenience (Strathman et al., 1994; Carmi & Arnon, 2014). In contrast, those who consider immediate consequences more prioritize short-term personal benefits, a tendency that has been linked to higher individual greenhouse gas emissions across multiple life domains (e.g., Joireman et al., 2004; Khachatryan et al., 2013; Sun et al., 2021). Engaging in an EC may therefore rather be related to the former than to the latter.

The Present Research

We set out to investigate the participants preferences to join an EC based on the above discussed dimensions and, additionally, on person-specific characteristics. Preference is understood as motivation to join an EC based on features that an EC entails. As this requires the provision of information on ECs, we prepared profiles of ECs based on the dimensions. These profiles were presented to Austrian participants in a quota-representative conjoint study to see, which aspects of an EC are particularly attractive.

For the dimensions and aspects, we formulated the following exploratory research question as the main goal of this study (see preregistration: https://osf.io/s3f42/overview?view_only=5f693813bc97459998735eff36e48a69):

¹ Note that Witesman and colleagues (2022) describe many facets of public service attitudes, values and practices, including management styles and belief in better opportunities for citizens. We focus on the *attitudes* dimension for public service only (dimension APS, Table A5 in Witesman et al., 2022).

RQ1: Which (a) social, (b) legal or (c) technical aspects of an EC profile stand out as particularly motivating for people to join an EC?

We also pretested all profile aspects in small preliminary pilot study, checking for their clarity in the formulations and obtaining initial evidence for motivation ratings. The results, as shown in the next section, were then used for more specific hypotheses.

As a secondary goal, we also wanted to gain initial evidence for potential person-specific factors that may affect motivation ratings beyond the aspects of an EC. Hence, we formulated the following research question:

RQ2: Which person-specific characteristics explain higher motivation to join an EC?

Following the pilot study, we describe the specific methods of how we aimed at answering these RQs using the conjoint study method.

Summary of the Pilot Study

We set up a pilot study with the goals to ii) refine the clarity and intelligibility of how we formulated the aspects in our profile descriptions and i) gain initial evidence for a motivation to join an energy community based solely on individual aspects of EC profiles. Importantly, we aimed for presenting the aspects individually and not in the context of other aspects of an EC profile. These exploratory goals were preregistered before the data collection (https://osf.io/9yd5m/overview?view_only=277f376d88f9427c92696973f98b8115).

Next, we set up an online survey in LimeSurvey (version 3, LimeSurvey GmbH, 2023), which we send around in Austrian online forums and via email distribution lists to gather a convenience sample of $N = 50$ participants, which we achieved ($N = 50$, $M_{\text{age}} = 42$ years, $SD_{\text{age}} = 14$ years, $n_{\text{female}} = 26$, $n_{\text{university degree}} = 38$). In the survey, we first obtained informed consent and gathered some demographic information. Second, we presented participants with the concept of ECs in a short paragraph. We also linked to more information by the Austrian Coordination Office for Energy Communities (see <https://energiegemeinschaften.gv.at/>). After an attention-check question, we directed participants to six pages that were always introduced the same way: “Imagine you are online on some webpages and you find an add by an Energy Community to join it. It advertises the following aspects regarding (...). How clearly understandable do you find these aspects and how motivated would you be to join the Energy Community upon reading these aspects?”

Specific features of the EC, that is, the aspects of several dimensions of the EC, were presented to the participants. They read all aspects of these dimensions and rated i) if they found their wording clear, and ii) if they felt motivated to join the EC on 7-point rating scales (from 1 “not at all” to 7 “very much”).

The detailed outcomes of the pilot study can be found in Table S3 in the supplemental materials (https://osf.io/853pe/overview?view_only=ca293d16e9ee4488b9aa2904825632ed). Here, we focus on the two most important outcomes of this pilot study. First, most wordings were already clear to participants, as indicated by ratings in the upper part of the rating scale (above scale midpoint

4). However, ratings for the motivation were partly quite low (below scale point 3). Hence, we adapted a few formulations for the main study, which resulted in the final dimensions and their aspects presented in Table 1: We formulated three social subdimensions, representing (A) community exchange, (B) composition, and (C) member's socio-economic background; two technical dimensions, representing (D) automatization and data and (E) energy use; and one legal dimension of (F) the legal form of the EC.

Second, through the pilot study, large difference in motivation ratings were obtained for two aspects in two dimensions: For the legal dimension (F), we found that participants strongly preferred (1) associations ($M = 5.62$, $SD = 1.46$) over (2) cooperatives ($M = 2.54$, $SD = 1.84$) and (3) companies ($M = 3.24$, $SD = 2.06$). And for the energy use dimension (E), we found that participants strongly preferred (2) comprehensive energy use ($M = 5.06$, $SD = 1.79$) instead of (1) limited energy usage (e.g., only for electricity) ($M = 2.80$, $SD = 1.67$).

Based on these results, we could formulate two specific hypotheses for RQ1:

H1: The legal EC form of an association leads to higher motivation ratings compared to the form of a cooperative and a company.

H2: A more comprehensive use of energy in ECs leads to higher motivation ratings than a more specific use (e.g., only for electricity).

Methods of the Conjoint Study

Online Set up

This study was set up in *LimeSurvey* (version 3, LimeSurvey, 2023) and experimental software *PsychoPy* via the online surface *Pavlovia* (Peirce et al., 2019), where the former is suited for general surveys and the latter is suited for more complex experimental online designs, including conjoint studies. We spread this survey via the panel provider *talk* (see <https://talkonlinepanel.com/at>) among the Austrian population. In LimeSurvey, we presented participants with a consent form, followed by several demographic questions (see Table S1).

Afterwards, we briefly introduced them to the main part of study by first describing the concept of ECs. This information was adapted from the website of the Austrian Coordination Office for Energy Communities (see <https://energiegemeinschaften.gv.at/>), which contains a comprehensive overview of the situation of ECs in Austria, and which we also linked to. Specifically, they read: "In an energy community, at least two partners (e.g., households, small businesses, municipalities) – and potentially up to several hundred members – join together to collectively produce, store, consume, and, if applicable, sell energy. The members rely on renewable energy sources, for example through solar panel systems installed on a multi-unit residential building or a housing block."

Table 1. Final dimensions used in the main study.

Dimension	Aspect 1	Aspect 2	Aspect 3
A (social)	Members of the energy community meet every six months for meetings. This infrequent exchange hardly leads to a sense of community among those involved.	Members of the energy community meet monthly for meetings. This frequent exchange strengthens the sense of community among the participants.	
B (social)	The energy community consists of households, house communities and/or small businesses.	The energy community is supported by a medium-sized company, which encourages citizens to participate.	In addition to various households, the municipality is also involved in the energy community and encourages citizens to participate.
C (social)	The members are mostly from middle and higher income brackets and show higher expertise in organizational and technical tasks.	The members are from lower, middle and higher income brackets and have varying levels of expertise in organizational and technical tasks.	
D (tech)	Technical aspects of the energy community are completely automated. Although they can be tracked using simple apps (e.g. on a cell phone), the technology is controlled and regulated by experts who have access to the members' data.	Technical aspects of the energy community are partially automated. They can be partially regulated via simple apps (e.g. on the cell phone). In addition, experts who have access to the data control and optimize other aspects.	Members have full control over the technical aspects. In order to optimize the settings, members must coordinate regularly. There is no automation (e.g. via apps), which ensures the protection of data.
E (tech)	The jointly generated energy is used for a central purpose - e.g. for electricity. This initially enables clear and transparent use, but is less efficient in the long term.	The jointly generated energy is used for multiple purposes – e.g., electricity, heating, cooling systems, etc. This is more complex at the beginning but more efficient in the long term.	
F (legal)	This energy community has the legal form of an association. Decisions are made by the general meeting and a board of directors, among others. There is no legally prescribed starting capital for new members. Making a profit may only be a secondary purpose. Profits generated are used for the community, but not for individual members. In the event of debts, the community is also liable with its assets, but not the individual members.	This energy community has the legal form of a cooperative. Decisions are made by the Board of Directors. There is no legally prescribed starting capital. Profits are not the aim of the community, but if these arise from the sale of renewable energy generated, they can be passed on to individual members. The individual members are liable for debts, not the energy community.	This energy community has the legal form of a limited liability company. Decisions are made by the general meeting. New members (shareholders) are required to contribute EUR 10,000 as statutory starting capital. Profits are distributed to the members in proportion to their contributions. The community is liable for debts with all its assets, but there is no personal liability of individual members.

Next, they were briefly introduced to the set-up of the conjoint part, where we showed them a hypothetical example of two EC profiles, including the rating scales to familiarize them with the look of the upcoming task. An attention check question verified participants had read the information on the ECs before. We then forwarded them to the conjoint part in PsychoPy.

On five pages, participants read about two profiles of ECs, rated which EC they felt more motivated to join (DV1 for each EC: “How motivated would you feel to joint this EC?”, 1 = “not at all motivated”, 7 = “very motivated”) and made a dichotomous choice which profile they preferred (DV 2: decision; 0 = not chosen, 1 = chosen). These profiles were randomly drawn from a pool of all possible profiles, which were 216 unique combinations based on six dimensions with two to three aspects each. They are all shown in Table 1 (see original German version in Table S2 and the depiction of EC profiles in Figure S1).

Afterwards, participants answered additional questions on their biospheric values (*bios*), their future and present orientation (consideration of future / immediate consequences, *cfc* / *cic*), as well as on their attitudes towards public service (*psa*). Bios, as well as *cfc* and *cic* were assessed with short scales with two to three items (see Brohmer et al., 2023a; Witesman et al., 2022), which we later used to build mean composite scores. We also had participants self-evaluate their competence regarding the EC topic on one item following the conjoint part. After the conclusion of the survey participants were sent back to the panel provider.

Participants and Power

We planned a diverse sample of the Austrian population, provided by an online panel provider (in our case Talk Online, <https://talkonlinepanel.com/at>). In our preregistration, we registered a sample size of a minimum of $N = 540$ participants (and up to 600, see preregistration: https://osf.io/s3f42/?view_only=5f693813bc97459998735eff36e48a69). This would provide sufficient statistical power ($1-\beta \geq .90$) for a conjoint study with five comparison tasks (i.e., profile pages to rate), where each profile has a maximum of three aspects, and where the anticipated average marginal component effect is small, $AMCE = 0.05$. Point estimates that fall below this threshold, will be interpreted as null effects.

Via the panel provider, we motivated $N = 2011$ people to click on the link to the study, of which $N = 1085$ reached the conjoint part. Of those, $N = 641$ completed the conjoint part.² There were some incomplete cases and several doublets, presumably because some participants started the study multiple times. We only counted the first trial, which left us with a final sample of $N = 554$. This sample consisted of 49% women ($n = 271$), 35% participants had a high school degree or college degree ($n = 195$), 52% came from the countryside with less than 10 000 residents in their area of living ($n = 287$). Their average age was $M = 49.39$ years ($SD = 16.94$, min = 18, max = 85). All further demographic information is available from Table S1.

² This dropout of 40% of the participants was expected as there was much information to read and process when going through the EC profiles (see Brohmer et al., 2023b).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics and Pearson Correlations.

	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mdn</i>	<i>min.</i>	<i>max.</i>	<i>r</i>				
							1.	2.	3.	4.	5.
1. motivation mean	554	3.80	1.05	4	1	6.40					
2. bios scale ($r = 0.75$)*	552	5.84	1.17	6	1	7	0.17				
3. psa scale ($\alpha = 0.91$)	553	5.39	1.17	5.50	1	7	0.32	0.71			
4. cfc scale ($\alpha = 0.83$)	548	5.10	1.11	5	1	7	0.24	0.58	0.63		
5. cic scale ($\alpha = 0.80$)	549	3.21	1.32	3.33	1	7	-0.08	-0.42	-0.37	-0.42	
6. competence	552	4.99	1.44	5	1	7	0.17	0.32	0.29	0.28	-0.10

Note: $r = 0.08$ is $p = 0.08$; all other correlations are $p < .02$; * scale consists of two items only; bios = biospheric values, psa = public service attitudes, cfc = consideration of future consequences, cic = consideration of immediate consequences; α refers to reliability coefficient Cronbach's α

Analysis Approach

We conducted descriptive analyses and built the mean composite scores for the scales following a reliability analysis. We then conducted the conjoint analysis, using all participant ratings to assess the motivation to join ECs for each dimensional aspect. Potential effects were then double-checked with the dichotomous decision variable. The resulting AMCE scores functioned as effect size to be compared. We also calculated interactions of dimensions to assess whether motivation ratings on some dimensions would be larger or lower depending on the scores of other dimensions. To assess individual-level differences, we additionally calculated multilevel models with the composite scores as predictors (similar to Brohmer et al. 2023b). These analyses were conducted using *R* (R Core Team, 2025) and the packages *cjoint* (Barari et al., 2023), *lme4* (Bates et al. 2023), and *jmv* (Selker et al., 2023).

Results

Descriptive statistics and correlations are depicted in Table 2. Main results for the conjoint study for the motivation rating are depicted in Figure 1A and B. The average scores for each aspect of the dimensions varied within one scale point ($3.5 < Ms < 4.5$), which had the grand mean of $M = 3.80$ (see Table 2) and the median was identical for each aspect, equating with the scale midpoint ($mdns = 4$). Hence, there was little variation in these means.

RQ1

When looking at the aspects per dimensions, we found evidence for effects in line with our hypotheses: Specifically, we found evidence for H1 that participants were less motivated to join an EC when it had the legal form of a cooperate or a company compared to when it was an association (see Figure 1B and D, dimension F). We also found evidence for H2 that participants preferred it slightly more when the generated energy of an EC could be used for a variety of

purposes (see Figure 1B and D, dimension E). In both cases, the statistically significant point estimates surpassed the predetermined threshold, $AMCEs > 0.05$.

For the other dimensions, we did not find consistent evidence for an effect. Particularly, in dimension C, motivation ratings seemed to be somewhat larger when the composition of the EC was more socio-economically diverse (Figure 1B), but this effect did not show for the dichotomous decision (Figure 1D). For dimensions A, B, and D, all estimates were even more closely clustered together. Finally, no interaction effect was found for the significant estimates (Figure 1C), indicating no detectable moderation effects of these dimensions.

For additional data exploration, we tried to identify auxiliary effects. First, we created a subset of those people, who carefully conducted the study based on their time of completion ($n = 395$). That is, we excluded participants who either took too little or too much time to finish the study (less than 30 and more than 180 seconds per conjoint page). Second, we looked at a subset of people, who evaluated themselves as competent in terms of ECs (self-evaluation ratings ≥ 5 ; $n = 362$). However, in both cases, the pattern of the motivation ratings did not differ from the previous results (see Figure 2A and B). The results from the dichotomous decision variable confirmed that differences were only present in dimension E and F (see Figure S4).

RQ2

Next, we conducted multilevel models for the person-specific predictors by nesting the ten participant ratings for the EC profiles in participants. We then run four models for each composite score. As a result, we found that PSA was associated positively with motivation to join an EC, $b = 0.321$, $p < .001$. Also, biospheric values and future orientation showed positive, but smaller effects, $bs \leq 0.112$, $ps < .05$. These results confirmed the correlations with the mean of all profile ratings (see Figure S2; see also Table S7 for numeric details).

From the strongest predictor, PSA, we created tercile bins and took the upper bin, i.e., the participants with the strongest ratings in favor of PSA ($n = 229$), which were also above the mean of the motivation ratings to join an EC (see Figure 2C). We reran the analysis for RQ1 with these participants to see, if the results would vary for them. However, the pattern of results remained identical for this subset of participants (see Figure 2D).

Discussion

ECs rise in popularity in many European countries. Because of that, it would be interesting to know what drives people's motivation to join ECs beyond economic factors such as financial incentives. Particularly, diverse social, legal and technical aspects of ECs could contribute to someone's decision to join, as well as individual person-specific inclinations. We set out to gather evidence using a conjoint study that is suitable for identifying preferred aspects among several dimensions. Confirming preliminary results from our pilot study, we found that two particular aspects of ECs stood out: the legal entity of an association was slightly preferred over other legal forms of

Figure 1. Main Results of the Conjoint Study.

(A) box plots for all motivation ratings; boxes represent the IQR with the median in the middle; red estimates are means with 95% confidence intervals (see Table S4); (B) AMCEs with 95% confidence intervals for motivation ratings with aspect 1 being the reference category; (C) AMCEs for motivation including interactions of significant dimensions (see Table S5); (D) AMCEs for decision to join the EC; point estimates larger than 0.05 are considered relevant; see Table 1 for aspects A1 to F3.

Figure 2. Further Analyses.

(A) AMCEs motivation for a subset of careful readers (less than 3 minutes and more than 30 seconds per page); (B) AMCEs motivation for a subset of knowledgeable participants; (C) fixed effect of public service attitudes in a multilevel linear model; (D) AMCEs for participants in the upper tercile of public service attitudes (see also Table S6; for lower tercile results see Figure S4).

ECs (i.e., a corporate or a company); and on the technical side, a comprehensive usage of energy was preferred over a focused usage. There was also limited evidence that a more socially diverse EC is preferred over an EC that only harbors upper-class people. In regard to person-specific factors, particularly positive attitudes towards public service were related to motivation to join an EC, followed by weaker effects for the consideration of future consequences in behavior as well as biospheric values.

Associations might be most attractive as they often provide participants with formally more agency and influence over internal decisions, compared to corporate or company structures. This is interesting as associations also do not necessarily provide possibilities for individual gains from energy production surplus. Potentially, the risk liabilities were seen as least pronounced in associations. Similarly relevant is the finding that people prefer EC structures for a comprehensive use of produced energy, not just a single focused use. Hence, it can be inferred that ECs that cover both electricity and heating for all purposes for one's household seem to be attractive as people do not have to manage several systems in parallel.

On the side of the person-specific variables, public service attitudes stood out as the strongest predictor for the motivation to join an EC. This is plausible as engagement in an EC, requires coordination and cooperation with other members. The social features of an EC presume their appreciation by individuals: the organization of energy production needs a level of social organization, including, who provides which number of photovoltaic installations and how exactly the energy is distributed among member households. In the same vein, future orientation in one's decision making and behavior and values in line with the environment partially contributed to the motivation to join an EC. This is not surprising as joining an EC requires an initial individual effort to achieve change. Positive future outcomes, that is, local green energy production independent from large suppliers and financial benefits, may only accumulate and fully unfold over time.

In general, the effects of the relevance of positive attitudes towards public service may reflect that positive beliefs related to the community and society as a whole become more pronounced among many people (Fabel et al., 2025). This growing sense of engagement challenges earlier assumptions about the public's role in the energy transition. In the past, people have mostly been seen as passive consumers, whereas newer approaches acknowledge their potential role as prosumers and active energy citizens (Devine-Wright, 2007; Ryghaug et al., 2018; Hamann et al., 2023). That way, ECs can be seen as both antecedent and consequence of energy citizenship. On one hand, they can act as a starting point by providing individuals with concrete opportunities to exercise their rights and responsibilities in the energy transition. On the other hand, through participation, ECs can shape their members' attitudes and motivations, potentially strengthening energy citizenship, as research suggests that individuals involved in energy communities tend to engage in more pro-environmental behaviors compared to those who are not (Middlemiss, 2011; Sloot et al., 2018).

Our study did not come without limitations. First, although our sample indicated to feel somewhat competent on the topic of EC, a follow-up study should account for what participants already know about ECs specifically. After all, despite high subjective competence ratings, it is possible that participants overestimate their knowledge in this domain with potentially detrimental consequences for green behavior (Bergquist, 2020).

Second, we did not include financial factors among the dimensions for the conjoint study. We did so because financial factors are a common focal point in such setups and likely distract participants from other aspects that bear importance as well. In our case, we deliberately focused on social, legal and technical aspects. However, a recent study on the broader topic of renewable energy projects (Vogel et al., 2024) showed that minimal initial investments, lower capital commitment periods and higher annual return in investments may increase the participation rate.

Third, our results show, that all EC aspects were rated as moderately attractive to the people on average: Ratings for the motivation to join clustered closely along the scale midpoint, but came with variation in both directions. While not uncommon for more complex conjoint studies, only considerable higher average ratings of aspects, would usually reflect noticeable higher preferences or motivations (as can be seen in financial factors too, see Brohmer et al., 2023b). On the contrary, average ratings close to the scale midpoint may indicate that many people likely did not yet concern themselves with a decision to partake in an EC actively. Hence, the effects we found may be stable, consistent, but likewise small.

Conclusions

This conjoint study was conducted to explore factors that motivate joining an EC. It revealed that ECs that allow comprehensive energy use and that have the legal setup of an association are most attractive. These effects were accompanied by person-specific factors: Public service attitudes, future orientation, and biospheric values contributed to participants' higher consideration to partake in an EC. Most effects were comparably small in nature, but potentially exemplified that engagement in energy projects that empower individuals in the role as prosumers is a viable route for future energy generation.

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